

DEFORMATION AND STRESS RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE LAMINATED SHELLS UNDER INTERNAL PRESSURE

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Abstract

This paper presents a theoretical study of the response of filament wound composite shells under internal pressure. Each layer of the material is generally cylindrically anisotropic. By using cylindrically anisotropic elasticity field equations and Lekhnitskii's stress functions, a system of sixth-order ordinary differential equations is obtained. The general expressions for the stresses and displacements in the laminated composite shells under internal pressure are discussed. Two composite systems, graphite/epoxy and glass/epoxy, are selected to demonstrate the influence of degree of material anisotropy and fiber orientations on the axial and induced twisting deformation. Stress distributions of $[45/-45]_s$ symmetric angle-ply fiber-reinforced laminated shells are shown to illustrate the effect of radius-to-thickness ratio.

1. Introduction

Shells of various constructions have been used extensively as load carrying structural components. With the unique characteristics of high strength/weight and stiffness/weight ratios in composite materials, composite laminated shells are receiving greater consideration for use in

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primary structures such as aircraft fuselages, solid rocket casings, submersibles and space vehicles. One of the concerns in structural design is devoted to developing analytical methods for determining the response under various loading conditions. Whitney and Halpin [1] have analyzed off-axis unidirectional two-layer angle-ply anisotropic tubes under various loading conditions based on Donnell's shallow shell approximations [2] to characterize the mechanical properties and behavior of fiber composites. Reuter [3] presented solutions for alternate-ply cylindrical shell under internal pressure using Donnell's theory. The stress field of a single layer anisotropic cylinder due to mechanical loadings was considered by Pagano [4]. Hull et al. [5] studied failure mechanisms of filament wound cylinder subjected to internal pressure. Hyer [6] has evaluated the stress distribution of cross-ply laminated shells under hydrostatic pressure. Recently Abu-Arja and Chandhuri [6] analyzed the behavior of moderately thick composite shells under internal pressure using shell theories including shear deformation.

The present paper studies the stress and deformation response of filament wound composite shells under internal pressure. In the next section, basic equations of cylindrically anisotropic elasticity are formulated based on Lekhnitskii's stress function approach. Solution structure of stresses and displacements is obtained in section 3. The axial and induced twisting deformation of two composite systems under internal pressure are studied in section 4. Stress and displacement distributions of $[\pm 45]_s$ glass/epoxy composite laminated shells are discussed in the paper.

2. Basic Equations

A laminated cylindrical shell consisting of fiber-reinforced laminae subjected to internal pressure is shown in Fig. 1. The strain-stress relations of each lamina with general cylindrical anisotropy are given by

$$\epsilon_i = S_{ij} \sigma_j, \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 6) \tag{1}$$

Fig. 1. Geometry of a Laminated Composite Shell under Internal Pressure

where S_{ij} are the compliance constants. A state of stresses in the cylindrical coordinate system (r, θ, z) is described by a stress tensor with components $\sigma_i = \{ \sigma_r, \sigma_\theta, \sigma_z, \tau_{\theta z}, \tau_{rz}, \tau_{r\theta} \}$. As a result of axisymmetric deformation, the displacements u_r, u_θ and w take the form:

$$u_r(r, \theta, z) = u_r(r, z), \quad u_\theta(r, \theta, z) = u_\theta(r, z), \quad w(r, \theta, z) = w(r, z) \quad (2)$$

The engineering strains, ϵ_i in equation (1) are related to these displacements by

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_1 = \epsilon_r &= \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r}, & \epsilon_2 = \epsilon_\theta &= \frac{u_r}{r}, & \epsilon_3 = \epsilon_z &= \frac{\partial w}{\partial z}, & \epsilon_4 = 2\gamma_{\theta z} &= \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} \\ \epsilon_5 = 2\gamma_{rz} &= \frac{\partial w}{\partial r}, & \epsilon_6 = 2\gamma_{r\theta} &= r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{u_\theta}{r} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The shell has a finite length and is under end axial loads acting in a plane normal to the z -axis. Surface tractions are independent of the z -axis. The shell is assumed to be long enough so that, in the region away from the ends, the Saint Venant's principle holds. Consequently, the stress components are independent of the z -coordinate. This class of problems may be formulated on the basis of theory of cylindrical anisotropic elasticity [8,9] using Lekhnitskii's stress potentials, F and ψ .

Following the procedure given in [8,9], one can establish a system of coupled governing ordinary differential equations in $F(r)$ and $\psi(r)$ for the individual lamina:

$$L'_4 F + L'_3 \psi = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$L''_3 F + L'_2 \psi = \frac{S_{34} A_3}{S_{33} r} - 2A_4$$

where L'_4, L'_3, L''_3 , and L'_2 are linear ordinary differential operations defined as

$$\begin{aligned} L'_4 &= \tilde{S}_{22} \frac{d^4}{dr^4} + 2\tilde{S}_{22} \frac{1}{r} \frac{d^3}{dr^3} - \tilde{S}_{11} \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \tilde{S}_{11} \frac{1}{r^3} \frac{d}{dr} \\ L'_3 &= -\tilde{S}_{24} \frac{d^3}{dr^3} + (\tilde{S}_{14} - 2\tilde{S}_{24}) \frac{1}{r} \frac{d^2}{dr^2} \\ L''_3 &= -\tilde{S}_{24} \frac{d^3}{dr^3} - (\tilde{S}_{14} + \tilde{S}_{24}) \frac{1}{r} \frac{d^2}{dr^2} \\ L'_2 &= \tilde{S}_{44} \frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \tilde{S}_{44} \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where A_3, A_4 pertain to uniform axial deformation and relative angle of rotation about the z -axis. The reduced compliance constants \tilde{S}_{ij} are defined as

$$\tilde{S}_{ij} = S_{ij} - \frac{S_{i3} S_{j3}}{S_{33}}, \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 4, 5, 6) \quad (6)$$

The stress components that relate the stress potentials may be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_r &= \frac{1}{r} \frac{dF}{dr}, \quad \sigma_\theta = \frac{d^2F}{dr^2}, \quad \tau_{\theta z} = -\frac{d\psi}{dr} \\ \sigma_z &= (A_3 - S_{13}\sigma_r - S_{23}\sigma_\theta - S_{34}\tau_{\theta z})/S_{33}\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

The displacements have the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}u_r &= U_r(r) + u_r^0 \\ u_\theta &= A_4 r z + U_\theta(r) + u_\theta^0 \\ w &= A_3 z + W(r) + w^0\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

The U_r , U_θ , and W represent the pure deformation field and the u_r^0 , u_θ^0 , w^0 , characterize rigid-body displacements.

3. Method of Solution

The solution of the coupled differential equations (4) can be expressed as

$$F(r) = a_1 r^3 + a_2 r^2 + C_0 r + \sum_{k=1}^2 C_k r^{1+\mu_k} \quad (9)$$

$$\psi(r) = b_1 r^2 + b_2 r + C_0 \eta_0 \ln r + \sum_{k=1}^2 C_k \eta_k r^{\mu_k} \quad (10)$$

where

$$\eta_0 = \frac{\tilde{S}_{11}}{\tilde{S}_{14}}, \quad \eta_k = \frac{\tilde{S}_{14} + \tilde{S}_{24} \mu_k}{\tilde{S}_{44}} \frac{1 + \mu_k}{\mu_k}, \quad (k=1,2)$$

$$\mu_{1,2} = \pm \left(\frac{\tilde{S}_{11} \tilde{S}_{44} - \tilde{S}_{14}^2}{\tilde{S}_{22} \tilde{S}_{44} - \tilde{S}_{24}^2} \right)^{1/2}$$

and the C 's are unknown constants to be determined later. Note that the μ_k are real due to the positive definiteness of \tilde{S}_{ij} . The constants a_1 , a_2 , b_1 and b_2 are related by the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned}3(\tilde{S}_{11} - 4\tilde{S}_{22})a_1 - 2(\tilde{S}_{14} - 2\tilde{S}_{24})b_1 &= 0 \\ 3(\tilde{S}_{14} + 2\tilde{S}_{24})a_1 - 2\tilde{S}_{44} b_1 &= A_4 \\ 2(\tilde{S}_{14} + \tilde{S}_{24})a_2 - \tilde{S}_{44} b_2 &= -S_{34}A_3/S_{33}\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

The stress components can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_r &= 3a_1r + 2a_2 + \frac{C_0}{r} + \sum_{k=1}^2 C_k(1 + \mu_k) r^{\mu_k-1} \\ \sigma_\theta &= 6a_1r + 2a_2 + \sum_{k=1}^2 C_k(1 + \mu_k) \mu_k r^{\mu_k-1} \\ \tau_{\theta z} &= -2b_1r - b_2 - C_0 \frac{\eta_0}{r} - \sum_{k=1}^2 C_k \eta_k \mu_k r^{\mu_k-1}\end{aligned}\quad (12)$$

The strain displacement relations of the Lekhnitskii's stress function approach provide

$$\epsilon_r = \frac{\partial U_r}{\partial r} = E_{11} + E_{12}r + \sum_{k=1}^2 C_k E_{13} r^{\mu_k-1} \quad (13)$$

$$\epsilon_\theta = \frac{U_r}{r} = (\tilde{S}_{12} - \tilde{S}_{24} \eta_0) \frac{C_0}{r} + E_{21} + E_{22}r + \sum_{k=1}^2 C_k E_{23} r^{\mu_k-1} \quad (14)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}E_{11} &= 2(\tilde{S}_{i1} + \tilde{S}_{i2})a_2 - \tilde{S}_{i4}b_2 + \frac{S_{i3}}{S_{33}} A_3 \\ E_{12} &= 3(\tilde{S}_{i1} + 2\tilde{S}_{i2})a_1 - 2\tilde{S}_{i4}b_1 \\ E_{13} &= \tilde{S}_{i1}(1 + \mu_k) + \tilde{S}_{i2}(1 + \mu_k)\mu_k - \tilde{S}_{i4}\eta_k\mu_k, \quad (i = 1, 2)\end{aligned}\quad (15)$$

Integrating equations (13) and equating equation (14) lead to the additional following relations

$$C_0 = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$2(\tilde{S}_{11} - \tilde{S}_{22})a_2 + (\tilde{S}_{24} - \tilde{S}_{14})b_2 = (S_{23} - S_{13})A_3/S_{33}$$

Combining equations (11) and equation (16) give

$$\begin{aligned}3a_1 &= \frac{2\tilde{S}_{24} - \tilde{S}_{14}}{(\tilde{S}_{11} - 4\tilde{S}_{22})\tilde{S}_{44} - (\tilde{S}_{14}^2 - 4\tilde{S}_{24}^2)} A_4 \equiv \kappa_2 A_4 \\ 2b_1 &= \frac{4\tilde{S}_{22} - \tilde{S}_{11}}{(\tilde{S}_{11} - 4\tilde{S}_{22})\tilde{S}_{44} - (\tilde{S}_{14}^2 - 4\tilde{S}_{24}^2)} A_4 \equiv \kappa_4 A_4 \\ 2a_2 &= \frac{S_{34}(\tilde{S}_{24} - \tilde{S}_{14}) - \tilde{S}_{44}(S_{23} - S_{13})}{(\tilde{S}_{14}^2 - \tilde{S}_{24}^2) - (\tilde{S}_{11} - \tilde{S}_{22})\tilde{S}_{44}} \frac{A_3}{S_{33}} \equiv \kappa_1 A_3\end{aligned}$$

$$b_2 = \frac{(S_{13}-S_{23})(\tilde{S}_{14}+\tilde{S}_{24})+(\tilde{S}_{22}-\tilde{S}_{11})S_{34}}{(\tilde{S}_{14}^2 - \tilde{S}_{24}^2) - (\tilde{S}_{11} - \tilde{S}_{22})\tilde{S}_{44}} \frac{A_3}{S_{33}} \equiv \kappa_3 A_3 \quad (17)$$

The final expression for the stresses and displacements can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_r &= \kappa_1 A_3 + \kappa_2 A_4 r + \sum_{k=1}^2 C_k (1 + \mu_k) r^{\mu_k - 1} \\ \sigma_\theta &= \kappa_1 A_3 + 2\kappa_2 A_4 r + \sum_{k=1}^2 C_k (1 + \mu_k) \mu_k r^{\mu_k - 1} \\ \tau_{\theta z} &= -\kappa_3 A_3 - \kappa_4 A_4 r - \sum_{k=1}^2 C_k \eta_k \mu_k r^{\mu_k - 1} \\ \sigma_z &= [1 - (S_{13} + S_{23})\kappa_1 + S_{34}\kappa_3] \frac{A_3}{S_{33}} - [(S_{13} + 2S_{23})\kappa_2 - S_{34}\kappa_4] \frac{A_4 r}{S_{33}} \\ &\quad - \sum_{k=1}^2 C_k [S_{13}(1+\mu_k) + S_{23}(1+\mu_k)\mu_k - S_{34}\eta_k \mu_k] \frac{r^{\mu_k - 1}}{S_{33}} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

The displacements excluding the rigid body displacements are expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} u_r &= D_1 A_3 r + D_2 A_4 r^2 + \sum_{k=1}^2 C_k [\tilde{S}_{11}(1 + \mu_k)/\mu_k + \tilde{S}_{12}(1 + \mu_k) - \tilde{S}_{14}\eta_k] r^{\mu_k} \\ u_\theta &= A_4 r z \\ w &= A_3 z \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} D_1 &= \frac{(\tilde{S}_{11} + \tilde{S}_{12})[S_{34}\tilde{S}_{24} + (S_{13} - S_{23})\tilde{S}_{44}]}{[(\tilde{S}_{14}^2 - \tilde{S}_{24}^2) - (\tilde{S}_{11} - \tilde{S}_{22})\tilde{S}_{44}]S_{33}} \\ &\quad - \frac{\tilde{S}_{14}[S_{34}(\tilde{S}_{12} + \tilde{S}_{22}) + (S_{13} - S_{23})(\tilde{S}_{14} + \tilde{S}_{24})]}{[(\tilde{S}_{14}^2 - \tilde{S}_{24}^2) - (\tilde{S}_{11} - \tilde{S}_{22})\tilde{S}_{44}]S_{33}} + \frac{S_{13}}{S_{33}} \\ D_2 &= \frac{(\tilde{S}_{11} + 2\tilde{S}_{12})\tilde{S}_{24} - (\tilde{S}_{12} + 2\tilde{S}_{22})\tilde{S}_{14}}{(\tilde{S}_{11} - 4\tilde{S}_{22})\tilde{S}_{44} - (\tilde{S}_{14}^2 - 4\tilde{S}_{24}^2)} \end{aligned}$$

Assuming that the bond between the laminae is perfect, the continuity conditions of the stress and displacement along the interface between k th and $(k+1)$ th lamina are given by:

$$\sigma_r^{(k)} = \sigma_r^{(k+1)}, \quad u_r^{(k)} = u_r^{(k+1)} \quad (20)$$

and

$$A_3^{(k)} = A_3^{(k+1)}, \quad A_4^{(k)} = A_4^{(k+1)} \quad (21)$$

The applied loadings at the ends of the composite shell are replaced by the following equivalent resultant forces and moments

$$\int_A \sigma_z r \, dr \, d\theta = P_z \quad (22)$$

$$\int_A \tau_{\theta z} r^2 \, dr \, d\theta = 0$$

where P_z is the applied axial load resulting from the internal pressure acting on the enclosure of the end cross sections with area A .

For an N -layer laminated cylindrical shell with $2N$ unknown constants and A_3, A_4 under consideration, these constants can be determined by imposing $2(N - 1)$ interfacial displacement and traction continuity conditions, equations (22) and two traction boundary conditions at the inner and outer cylindrical surfaces. Three stress components of an off-axis unidirectional shell by satisfying two traction boundary conditions at the inner and outer cylindrical surfaces are given in Appendix 1.

4. Results and Discussions

The method developed in the previous section is implemented for studying cylindrical composite laminated shells with end closures under internal pressure. The axial load exerted by the internal pressure upon the ends of cross section can be simulated as $P_z = \pi(R - \frac{h}{2})^2 p_i$, where p_i is the magnitude of the internal pressure. Graphite/epoxy and glass/epoxy composite materials with high and low material anisotropy are used for numerical calculations and their material properties are listed as follows:

	Graphite/Epoxy	Glass/Epoxy
E_L (Gpa)	172.375	41.37
E_T (Gpa)	6.895	13.79
E_Z (Gpa)	6.895	13.79
G_{LT} (Gpa)	3.448	5.516
G_{LZ} (Gpa)	3.448	5.516
G_{TZ} (Gpa)	1.379	2.758
ν_{LT}	0.25	0.25
ν_{LZ}	0.25	0.25
ν_{TZ}	0.25	0.25

where $L, T,$ and Z refer to material principal axes along fiber, transverse, and thickness direction respectively, and ν_{LT} is the Poisson's ratio for transverse strain in the T -direction

when stressed in the L-direction. The lamination angle α shown in Fig. 1 is measured in the counter-clockwise direction from the longitudinal direction of the shell.

To gain insight into the effects of curvilinear material anisotropy, fiber orientation, and stacking sequence, the axial and induced twisting deformation will be first studied in detail. For the case of composite shells with all off-angle α , Figs. 2 and 3 illustrate the extensional and twisting deformation of graphite/epoxy and glass/epoxy composites for mid-radius R-to-thickness ratio, $S = 10$. In Fig. 2, the extensional deformation for graphite/epoxy remains almost the same value in the region $0 \leq \alpha \leq 15^\circ$ and then increases monotonically. However, for glass/epoxy, the deformation decreases in the region from 0° to 26° and then increases. A relatively large induced twisting deformation of the off-axis unidirectional graphite/epoxy composite shells due to strong material anisotropy is shown in Fig. 3. The twisting deformation reaches maximum values at $\alpha \approx 52^\circ$ and 57° for graphite/epoxy and glass/epoxy respectively. The deformation behaviors of $[\pm\alpha]_S$ layup for these two composite systems are demonstrated in Figs. 4 to 5. A wide range of shortening deformation $5^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 53^\circ$ due to Poisson effect for graphite/epoxy under internal pressure can be seen in Fig. 4. For low anisotropy of the glass/epoxy material, a smaller range of shortening deformation $24^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 45^\circ$ is observed in the figure. The twisting deformation is relatively small due to the symmetric layup. Reversal of induced twisting deformation occurs from $\alpha = 9.5^\circ$ to $\alpha = 36^\circ$ for graphite/epoxy shown in Fig. 5. The figure also shows that the twisting deformation has highest value at $\alpha \approx 82.5^\circ$ and large variations as the angle approaches to 90° . No reversal of twisting deformation for glass/epoxy is found in Fig. 5. Figures 6 and 7 illustrate the axial and induced twisting deformation for $[\alpha/-\alpha]$ unsymmetric laminated shell of graphite/epoxy and glass/epoxy composites. Because of the nature of the layup, the shells exhibit coupling between stretching and twisting. Since the extensional stiffness is one order of magnitude higher than the coupling stiffness, variations of axial deformation with fiber orientation shown in Fig. 6 have almost the same curves as those of $[\alpha/-\alpha]_S$. In Fig. 7, reversal of twisting deformation occurs in most of the angles studied for graphite/epoxy and no reversal of twisting deformation for glass/epoxy is found in the figure. The effect of off-axis angle α on the stress distributions for graphite/epoxy composite shells with $S = 4$ is summarized in Figs. 8 and 9. The distributions of in-plane stress σ_θ through the thickness for five different α are shown in Fig. 8. The largest variation for all the cases studied is for $\alpha = 60^\circ$. The profile of σ_θ distribution exhibits compressive stress state at the outer radius. The steepest $\tau_{\theta z}$ stress distribution through the thickness occurs at $\alpha = 45^\circ$.

The symmetrical $[45/-45]_S$ angle-ply composite laminated shell is selected here as another example because of technical importance. The σ_r distribution through the thickness for three values of S is illustrated in Fig. 10. As the S increases, the distribution tends to vary linearly through the thickness direction. Figs. 11 and 12 depict the distributions of in-plane stresses σ_θ and $\tau_{\theta z}$ through the thickness. Slight discontinuity of σ_θ across the 45/-45 interface is shown in Fig. 11. As the shell becomes thinner, the σ_θ approaches a uniform distribution

through the thickness and is in agreement with the results obtained from simple strength of materials approach. It is found that in Fig. 12 that the $\tau_{\theta z}$ has the same order of magnitude as the σ_r and σ_θ . The distribution changes significantly with the thickness direction and alters its sign across the interface.

5. Summary and Conclusions

An analytical study of the deformation and stress response in laminated cylindrical shells under internal pressure has been presented. Formulations of the problem are based on exact anisotropic elasticity equations with the aid of Lekhnitskii's stress functions. In general, stress components σ_r , σ_θ , σ_z , and $\tau_{\theta z}$ and accompanying axial and twisting deformations will all be present in the composite shells subjected to the internal pressure. Two composite systems, graphite/epoxy and glass/epoxy, are selected to demonstrate the influence of material anisotropy and fiber orientations on the axial and twisting deformation. As is expected, materials with low anisotropy usually have small induced twisting deformation. Depending on the fiber orientations the shell may experience shortening axial deformation or reversed twisting deformation under internal pressure. The results also show that for the case of $[\alpha]$ composite shells the structure induces severe twisting deformation under internal pressure. Even for $[\pm\alpha]_s$ symmetric angle-ply laminated shells the structure yields small degree of twisting deformation. Stress distributions of symmetric $[45/-45]_s$ graphite/epoxy composite shells have been examined in detail. For the case studied, for very thin shells, the interlaminar normal stress distribution exhibits linear variation through the thickness and the in-plane stresses can be modelled from simple strength-of-material approach.

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Appendix 1

$$\sigma_r = \frac{p_i c^{\mu+1}}{1 - c^{2\mu}} (\rho^{\mu-1} - \rho^{-\mu-1})$$

$$+ \kappa_1 A_3 \left(1 - \frac{1 - c^{\mu+1}}{1 - c^{2\mu}} \rho^{\mu-1} - \frac{1 - c^{-\mu+1}}{1 - c^{-2\mu}} \rho^{-\mu-1} \right)$$

$$+ \kappa_2 A_4 \left(\rho - \frac{1 - c^{\mu+2}}{1 - c^{2\mu}} \rho^{\mu-1} - \frac{1 - c^{-\mu+2}}{1 - c^{-2\mu}} \rho^{-\mu-1} \right) b$$

$$\sigma_\theta = \frac{p_i \mu c^{\mu+1}}{1 - c^{2\mu}} (\rho^{\mu-1} + \rho^{-\mu-1})$$

$$+ \kappa_1 A_3 \left(1 - \frac{1 - c^{\mu+1}}{1 - c^{2\mu}} \mu \rho^{\mu-1} + \frac{1 - c^{-\mu+1}}{1 - c^{-2\mu}} \mu \rho^{-\mu-1} \right)$$

$$+ \kappa_2 A_4 \left(2\rho - \frac{1 - c^{\mu+2}}{1 - c^{2\mu}} \mu \rho^{\mu-1} + \frac{1 - c^{-\mu+2}}{1 - c^{-2\mu}} \mu \rho^{-\mu-1} \right) b$$

$$\tau_{\theta z} = \frac{-p_i \mu c^{\mu+1}}{1 - c^{2\mu}} \left(\frac{\eta_1}{1 + \mu} \rho^{\mu-1} + \frac{\eta_2}{1 - \mu} \rho^{-\mu-1} \right)$$

$$- \kappa_3 A_3 \left(1 - \frac{\kappa_1}{\kappa_3} \frac{1 - c^{\mu+1}}{(1 + \mu)(1 - c^{2\mu})} \eta_1 \mu \rho^{\mu-1} + \frac{\kappa_1}{\kappa_3} \frac{1 - c^{-\mu+1}}{(1 - \mu)(1 - c^{-2\mu})} \eta_2 \mu \rho^{-\mu-1} \right)$$

$$- \kappa_4 A_4 \left(\rho - \frac{\kappa_2}{\kappa_4} \frac{1 - c^{\mu+2}}{(1 + \mu)(1 - c^{2\mu})} \eta_1 \mu \rho^{\mu-1} + \frac{\kappa_2}{\kappa_4} \frac{1 - c^{-\mu+2}}{(1 - \mu)(1 - c^{-2\mu})} \eta_2 \mu \rho^{-\mu-1} \right) b$$

where a, b are inner and outer radii; respectively, $c = \frac{a}{b}$, $\rho = \frac{r}{b}$, $\mu \equiv \mu_1$.

Fig. 2. Axial Deformation of $[\alpha]$ Composite Cylindrical Shell

Fig. 3. Induced Twisting Deformation of $[\alpha]$ Composite Cylindrical Shell

Fig. 4. Axial Deformation of $[\alpha/-\alpha]_s$ Composite Cylindrical Shell

Fig. 5. Induced Twisting Deformation of $[\alpha/-\alpha]_s$ Composite Cylindrical Shell

Fig. 6. Axial Deformation of $[\alpha/-\alpha]$ Composite Cylindrical Shell

Fig. 7. Induced Twisting Deformation of $[\alpha/-\alpha]$ Composite Cylindrical Shell

Fig. 8. The Effect of Fiber Angle on σ_{θ} Stress Distribution through the Thickness in Off-Axis Unidirectional Composite Shell

Fig. 9. The Effect of Fiber Angle on $\tau_{\theta z}$ Stress Distribution through the Thickness in Off-Axis Unidirectional Composite Shell

Fig. 10. Distributions of Interlaminar Normal Stress σ_r through the Thickness Direction in [45/-45]_s Graphite/Epoxy Composite

Fig. 11. Distributions of In-Plane Stress σ_{θ} through the Thickness Direction in [45/-45]_s Graphite/Epoxy Composite

Fig. 12. Distributions of In-Plane Stress $\tau_{\theta z}$ through the Thickness Direction in [45/-45]_s Graphite/Epoxy Composite